

COLORIMÉTRIC ESTIMATION OF IRON BY DIPHENYLTHIOVIOLURIC ACID

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Diphenylthiovioluric acid has been used for the colorimetric estimation of iron in the ferrous state in a photoelectric colorimeter. The maximum absorption due to the coloured complex is in the region of 660 m μ . The estimation of iron can be accurately carried out when the concentration is between 0.2 and 1.2 parts per million parts of the solvent. The effect of various ions and other factors on the coloured complex has also been studied.

Preparation of complexes of diphenylthiovioluric acid with many metals was reported by Ghambhir and Singh (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1946, 25A, 330). It was found that ferrous iron formed a deep blue insoluble complex which was precipitated on addition of a solution of the ammonium salt of diphenylthiovioluric acid to an aqueous solution of a ferrous salt.

The complex dissolves in acetone or in aqueous acetone, forming a deep bluish green solution. A large excess of the reagent is needed for full development of colour. Maximum absorption due to the coloured complex takes place in the region of 660 m μ , and this region remains unaltered by an excess of the reagent. Full development of colour is instantaneous and the intensity of colour remains constant for several days. For these estimations, iron must be in the ferrous state, and if it is in the ferric condition, it can be reduced by hydroquinone, an excess of which does not interfere. It was found that several cations and anions had no effect on the colour intensity, but some interfered.

EXPERIMENTAL

The optical density measurements were carried out with a Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter, of which the scale reading was directly proportional to the optical density of the coloured solution as determined by the photo-electric cell. Since the optical density is proportional to the concentration of the coloured substance (Beer's law), the scale readings are therefore proportional to the concentration of the substance under examination.

The chemicals used were all of the reagent quality. Standard solutions of iron were prepared from ferrous ammonium sulphate (A.R., B.D.H.) and the iron content was checked volumetrically by titrating against standard potassium permanganate.

Instead of using the ammonium salt of diphenylthiovioluric acid, it was found that the acid itself could be used. Solutions of diphenylthiovioluric acid were prepared in acetone (0.5%). Standard solutions of various ions were prepared from nitrates, sulphates or chlorides in the case of cations, and from the sodium or potassium salts in the case of anions.

Region of Maximum Absorption.—A standard solution (5 c.c.) of Mohr's salt containing an appropriate quantity of iron was taken for each estimation and 5 c.c. of acetone solution of diphenylthiovioluric acid containing an excess of the reagent was added to it. The acetone concentration in the final solutions was maintained at 50% throughout to facilitate comparison.

The bluish green colour, formed by the reagent with iron in 50% acetone solution, showed maximum absorption in the region of 660 m μ . Varying amounts of iron and the reagent had no influence on the region of maximum absorption. The observations are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Wave-length (m μ) ...	490	515	550	575	595	640	660
		Fe ²⁺ soln. = 4 p.p.m.					
Col. readings ...	380	305	340	390	450	340	280
		Fe ³⁺ soln. = 2 p.p.m.					
Col. readings ...	270	190	165	195	240	222	143

Effect of Reagent.—It was found that a large excess of the reagent was necessary for full colour development, due probably to the reversibility of the reaction :

From the observations, recorded in Table II, it will be seen that about 200 times the theoretical quantity of the reagent is necessary for full colour development. Even larger quantities of the reagent do not interfere.

TABLE II

Reagent soln. taken (in c.c.)	1	2	3	4	5	6
Col. readings for Fe ²⁺ soln. = 2 p.p.m.	45	72	98	142	143	143
Col. readings for Fe ²⁺ soln. = 1 p.p.m.	27	52	73	73	73	73

Beer's Law.—That Beer's law is obeyed by the colour system is shown by the fact that the colorimetric readings are directly proportional to the amount of iron present in the solution, as shown by the observations recorded in Table III. The iron content of the solution should be between 0.1 and 1.2 $\mu\text{g./c.c.}$ In case the amount of iron is more than this limit, Beer's law is obeyed only approximately.

TABLE III

Iron soln. taken (in c.c.)	1	2	3	4	5
Col. readings for Fe ²⁺ soln. = 2 p.p.m.	30	60	88	116	145
Col. readings for Fe ²⁺ soln. = 4 p.p.m.	61	117	175	226	282

Effect of Time and Temperature on the Coloured System.—Full colour development took place immediately after the addition of the reagent. The absorption due to the coloured system was found to remain constant for days together for concentrations

of iron greater than 0.2 p.p.m. The ratio of acetone and water in the final solutions was maintained at 50:50. Experiments were carried out with solutions of concentrations of 4 p.p.m. and 2 p.p.m., keeping the quantity of the reagent solution the same in both cases (5 c.c. of 1% soln.). The coloured complex in solution was exposed to diffused day light and readings were taken after an interval of 10 minutes. The readings were found to be constant for two days, after which no readings were taken.

As regards the effect of temperature, it was found that a change between 10° and 50° did not alter the colorimetric readings.

Effect of Change of p_H on the Colour System.—Very dilute solutions of Merck's pure HCl and NaOH were prepared to study the effect of variation of p_H on the colour system. The concentrations of iron and the reagent and the proportions of acetone and water in the final solutions were kept constant throughout. The results are graphically represented in Fig. 1.

From the above figure, it can be seen that the p_H of the solution must be adjusted between 3.1 and 6.0 for correct estimations.

Effect of Reducing Agents.—As already pointed out, iron must be in the ferrous state for these estimations. The effect of reducing agents on the colour system was therefore studied. It was found that hydroquinone worked best for reduction of iron. The quantity of hydroquinone must be at least 50 times the quantity of iron present for complete reduction so that the full colour development may take place. A much larger quantity of hydroquinone can, however, be tolerated.

Reduction of iron with hydroxylamine hydrochloride or hydrazine hydrochloride was also carried out, but the solution became acidic, and p_H of the solutions had to be adjusted within the required limits. Detailed investigations with these reducing agents were not carried out.

Effect of various Anions.—The effect of various anions on the colour system was studied by the addition of sodium or potassium salt of the corresponding ion in different quantities before measuring the colour density. It was found that chloride, bromide, iodide, nitrate, nitrite, sulphate and thiocyanate did not interfere even if present in relatively large quantities (as much as 100 times the quantity of iron). On the other hand, oxalate, citrate and tartrate interfered even if present in small quantities. The measurements were carried out under appropriate conditions, discussed above.

Effect of various Cations.—The effect of different cations was similarly studied by adding soluble salts of the metals to the iron solution. It was found that ions of the alkali and alkaline earth metals caused no interference even at relatively high concentrations (as much as 500 p.p.m. for 2 p.p.m. of iron), whereas those of copper, silver and gold showed marked interference. Copper cannot be tolerated at all; silver can be tolerated up to 10 p.p.m. and gold up to 20 p.p.m. Aluminium and chromium can be tolerated up to 20 and 40 p.p.m. respectively, whereas nickel, zinc, lead, mercury, stannic, manganese and magnesium can be tolerated even up to concentrations of 100 times that of iron.

Comparison with other Reagents.—The characteristics of common colorimetric reagents for iron have been compared with those of diphenylthiovioluric acid in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Reagent.	Sensivity.	Stability of colour.	pH range.	Effect of excess.	Beer's law.
KCNS	1 p.p.m.	Fades rapidly	0.05-1N	Increases intensity	Slight deviation.
Dipyridyl	1	1 year	3-9	None	Obeded.
<i>o</i> -Phenanthroline	2	6 months or more	2-9	None	Do
Salicylaldoxime	4	1 day	6.1-6.6	None	Do
Salicylic acid	12	2-3 days	2.5-2.7	Increases intensity	Do
Diphenylthio- violuric acid	0.2	Very stable	3.1-6.0	Increases intensity	Do

The above table shows that diphenylthiovioluric acid has many advantages over some of the well known reagents which are used for this purpose.

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